

Strategies for Ensuring the Effectiveness of Public Policies and Initiatives in Supporting Hybrid Entrepreneurs in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province

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Hybrid entrepreneurship has become increasingly prevalent in South Africa. While government policies and programs are instrumental in fostering entrepreneurship, there is limited focus on policies tailored to the unique needs of hybrid entrepreneurs, especially in rural contexts. This study investigates how public policies and initiatives can be optimised to better support hybrid entrepreneurs in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province. A qualitative approach was adopted, employing an exploratory phenomenological research design. Participants, including hybrid entrepreneurs and government officials, were selected through purposive sampling. Data were gathered via semi-structured interviews and analysed using thematic analysis with ATLAS.ti software. The study identifies key strategies to enhance policy effectiveness, including the development of inclusive funding and mentorship programs, targeted skills development and training, increased policy awareness, improved competition frameworks, and stronger public-private sector partnerships.

Keywords: Hybrid entrepreneurs, effectiveness, entrepreneurial support, public policies, strategies

To promote social and economic outcomes and the quality of life for citizens and businesses, the government implements regulatory policies, which involve the use of laws and other mechanisms (Noll, 2021; Wasserbaur, Sakao, & Milios, 2022). Preserving order and prohibiting certain actions that present a risk to society are the main objectives of regulatory policy. Government restrictions are put in place on specific groups or corporations that engage in activities that negatively impact a nation's social and political stability (Noll, 2021). Graafland and Verbruggen (2022) state that an additional objective of the policy is to create a free-market economy and maintain economic activity and markets by imposing limitations on monopolistic behaviours.

Public policy plays a vital role in the entrepreneurial ecosystem (Elnadi & Gheith, 2021). The impact of policies on entrepreneurship

can be positive or negative, depending on their formulation and execution (Fkun, Yusuf, Rukmana, Putri, & Harahap, 2023; Owen, Vedanthachari, & Hussain, 2023). Nevertheless, the business policies of hybrid entrepreneurs, which entail individuals participating in self-employment activities while simultaneously holding a primary job for monetary compensation (Demir et al., 2022) are contingent upon and often influenced by the public policies within the economy (Du et al., 2016). Consequently, the policies enacted by the government are external in nature and cannot be directly influenced by entrepreneurs or business individuals within the economy (Fkun et al., 2023).

According to Sadiku-Doshi and Ramadhani's (2020), study, literature generally agrees that public policies are necessary for the expansion and success of entrepreneurial endeavors. However, hybrid entrepreneurs, a rapidly growing group of businesspeople have not attracted much attention in the literature (Bögenhold, 2019; Demir, Werner, Kraus, & Jones, 2020). The prevalence of hybrid entrepreneurship in the real world (Nordstrom, Siren, Thorgren, and Wincent, 2016; Ferreira, 2020) suggests that many business owners are opting to use hybrid entrepreneurship to launch their organisations. Despite the growing interest in entrepreneurship and the role of public policies in supporting entrepreneurs in South Africa, there is little research that specifically focuses on hybrid entrepreneurship and the efficacy of public policies and initiatives in supporting hybrid entrepreneurs (Solesvik, 2017; Cestino, 2019). This study aims to fill this gap by examining strategies for ensuring the effectiveness of public policies and initiatives in supporting hybrid entrepreneurs in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province. By addressing these gaps, this study can contribute to the development of a policy framework to promote the success of hybrid entrepreneurship in the Vhembe district, Limpopo province, South Africa.

Review of Literature

According to Maritz et al. (2023), the phenomenon of hybrid

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entrepreneurship has not been the recipient of sufficient attention from policymakers. Therefore, there is a pressing need to enhance awareness surrounding hybrid entrepreneurship as a viable option for full-time entrepreneurial pursuits. Hybrid entrepreneurs encounter psychological challenges due to the demands imposed by their dual employment status (Ardianti et al., 2022; Stephan, Rauch, & Hatak, 2023). Furthermore, it is worth noting that hybrid entrepreneurs often operate in suboptimal work environments. Therefore, it is imperative to develop and foster ecosystems that actively promote and support hybrid entrepreneurship. Due to the lack of literature that focuses on public policies that support hybrid entrepreneurship, literature on entrepreneurship was used.

Effectiveness of Public Policies in Supporting Entrepreneurial Activities

Economic growth has benefited from the laws, general policies, and legislative frameworks that governments have created to encourage entrepreneurial ventures (Salami, Ekakitie, & Ebinim, 2023). According to the Schumpeterian theory of the state and the capitalist perspective on how governments can support entrepreneurship's impact on economic growth, "private sector entrepreneurship and public-sector government represent two sides of a comprehensive development process" (Ebner, 2006). Additionally, researchers emphasise how the government supports entrepreneurship, whether it be through grants, training programs, counselling services, or less restrictive regulations. This has been crucial for liberalising emerging economies since it opens doors for international investment, introduces innovative technology, and substantially boosts employment rates (Campos, Braga, Correia, Ratten, & Marques, 2021). The evaluation criteria of the South African government should encompass the influence of support programs on entrepreneurial intention, as the latter serves as a precursor to entrepreneurial behaviour (Mothibi, Malebana, & Rankhumise, 2025). This inclusion enables policymakers to ascertain the extent to which support programs yield the intended outcomes on entrepreneurial intention and its underlying factors (Losa, 2025). Despite the existence of various forms of government assistance, many small business owners have challenges accessing it. This is primarily because of low awareness, the lack of information on support institutions and programs, the high costs of these initiatives, and the limited involvement of commercial banks (Malebana, 2017; Finmark Trust, 2010). The amount of funding available to entrepreneurs can also be influenced by governmental laws. Tax incentives, as an example, can promote more investment in the startup environment. The efficiency of entrepreneurial networks can also be impacted by the availability of funding because these networks require an adequate number of entrepreneurs and investors to be successful (Sreenivasan & Suresh, 2023). The efficacy of governmental policies, funding initiatives, and interconnectivity hinges upon their capacity to function in a harmonized manner (Arwan, Mawardi, & Bafadhal, 2018; Cavallo, Ghezzi, & Balocco, 2019; Knox & Arshed, 2022). The attainment of effective coordination necessitates robust leadership and collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including governmental agencies, investors, entrepreneurs, and other supporting institutions (Dzapasi, 2019).

The presence of public policies, financial backing, and networks assumes paramount importance in establishing a conducive environment for entrepreneurial endeavours (Hermanto, 2017; Wei, 2022).

Proposed Theory for the Study

The current study was underpinned by the "Schumpeter effect" theory. According to the Schumpeterian theory of the state and the capitalist perspective on how governments can support entrepreneurship's impact on economic growth, "private sector entrepreneurship and public-sector government represent two sides of a comprehensive development process" (Ebner, 2006). Garofoli (1994) and Audretsch and Fritsch (1994) indicate that the creation of new businesses is inversely related to unemployment rates, suggesting that the establishment of these ventures enhances job opportunities and significantly reduces unemployment levels. Similarly, Lucas (1978) and Jovanovic (1982) argue that a high prevalence of unemployment in society is associated with a lack of entrepreneurial activities. Essentially, when there is a low inclination towards starting businesses, unemployment rates tend to be high. These findings suggest that unemployed individuals may remain so due to their limited human capital resources and entrepreneurial skills necessary for initiating and sustaining new enterprises. However, this study specifically focuses on individuals pursuing entrepreneurship while concurrently holding full-time employment.

Method

This section delved into the various research methodologies implemented in this investigation to address the identified research issue. It further elaborated on the critical techniques utilised for gathering and analysing data.

The area of interest for this study was the Vhembe District in Limpopo Province, South Africa, which comprise of the four local municipalities, namely, Makhado, Thulamela, Musina, and Collins Chabane. The study area was selected because it encourages entrepreneurial successes and developments. The chosen district municipality has a significant impact on the provincial economy and the South African economy through its entrepreneurial ecosystem.

This study adopted an interpretivist paradigm, focusing on clarifying and interpreting the meaning of the phenomenon being examined, which was the objective the researcher sought to accomplish (Hossain, Alam, & Ali, 2024).

Research Design

This study adopted an exploratory phenomenological research design, which is utilised when studies are intended to explore a relatively unfamiliar area. The study also employed qualitative research, which is defined as an interactive process in which improved understanding of the scientific community is achieved by making new significant directions resulting from getting closer to the phenomenon studied (Aspers & Corte, 2019). Qualitative method was selected to allow the researcher to explore and better understand the complexity of the phenomenon (Mohajan, 2018).

The study's target population is as follows:

Hybrid Entrepreneurs: are those who are actively running a business or engaging in entrepreneurial pursuits while also pursuing other types of employment or non-entrepreneurial endeavours.

Officials from the Government: People in charge of creating, enacting, or managing laws and initiatives that encourage entrepreneurship in the Vhembe District, Limpopo province.

This study employed purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a non-probability technique that is chosen by the researcher

to intentionally select participants who are knowledgeable about the phenomenon being studied (Gill, 2020). Purposive sampling was selected because it allows the researcher to select participants most suitable and beneficial for the study.

Creswell (2013) argues that phenomenological investigations necessitate a minimum of five participants and a maximum of twenty-five participants. Additionally, Malterud, Siersma, and Guesson (2016) propose that qualitative research utilizing interviews should adhere to a suggested sample size of six participants. As a result, this study embraced a sample of sixteen participants, and data collection ceased when data saturation, as outlined by Gill (2020) was achieved.

Measure

Interviews were conducted through face-to-face interaction and through telephonic communication using semi-structured interview guides. This allowed the researcher the opportunity to further gain a deeper understanding of the study topic and provide an opportunity for further probing.

The in-depth interviews were recorded using a digital voice recorder and were transcribed using Microsoft Word. ATLAS.ti version 8 was used to analyse data. The software enables researchers to assign codes or labels to text, sound, pictures, or video; to search these codes for patterns; and to construct classifications of codes that reflect stable models of the conceptual structure of the underlying data (Kimmel, 2012; Marathe & Toyama, 2018).

Measures to Ensure Trustworthiness

To ensure the credibility of the findings, the interpretations were

cross-referenced with the unprocessed data gathered. To enhance the credibility of qualitative thematic analysis, researchers devise not only data collection strategies capable of acquiring representations but also transparent procedures for categorising and deriving conclusions from the raw data (Zhang & Wildermuth, 2009). To ensure credibility in this study, the researcher hired a research assistant when gathering data and used thematic analysis to interpret the data collected. The researcher employed a semi-structured interview guide throughout the duration of the research to delve deeper into the perspectives, understanding, and experiences of the respondents. This ensured that the researcher could draw results that are reliable and dependable.

Ethical Considerations

The entire study process takes ethical considerations into account. This includes getting the participants' free and informed consent and guaranteeing the privacy and anonymity of study data.

Results

This section presents the study's findings regarding strategies to enhance the effectiveness of public policies and initiatives supporting hybrid entrepreneurs in the Vhembe District Municipality. The results are based on interviews with sixteen participants from diverse sectors, as detailed in Table 1. Direct quotations from participants are provided to substantiate the description of these themes. A visual representation of results derived from ATLAS.ti is indicated in Figure 1.

Table 1
Participants' Demographics Summary

	Business Type	Field of Work	Gender	Age	Years of Business Experience
1	Online clothing	Financial Sector	Male	35	2
2	Fashion Retail	Private sector	Female	28	3
3	Rental Properties	Academic sector	Male	40	7
4	Transportation	Transportation Sector	Male	36	6
5	Educational Services	Academic sector	Female	32	4
6	IT	private sector	Male	45	1
7	Research assistance	Academic sector	Female	29	2
8	Construction	Academic	Male	33	3
9	Marketing services and cleaning	Mining sector	Female	34	3
10	Security	Municipality	Male	41	8
11	Social entrepreneurship	Academic	Male	27	2
12	Salon	Basic education.	Female	25	4
13	Transport	Basic education.	Male	38	5
14	Spaza Shop	Retail Sector	Male	39	5
15	Agriculture	Farming	Female	50	15
16	Poultry business	Construction industry	Male	44	12

Figure 1

Strategies for Ensuring Effectiveness of Public Policies.

Fostering fair Competition and Reducing Bias

Hybrid entrepreneurs are deemed to support competitiveness and equity against other competitors, primarily when it comes to issues related to government contracts and tenders. Business needs priority refers to the recognition that while prioritising businesses which provide scarce skills, they must not be hindered by systematic bias or subcontracting structures:

P8: "Some of the businesses that we offer require scarce skills. We need to be prioritised because we are not just... we find ourselves being subcontracted to someone who does not even know anything, just because maybe you meet all the criteria, maybe when he looks at some of the unemployed. There is so for other companies just because maybe we may not qualify to do those things as a principal contractor that is maybe contracted to the government."

Another participant also stressed the need for fair competition and called for a system that will let companies be fairly evaluated, including whether they are compliant with the existing standards.:

P3: "I just think that the equality in terms of competition, that if we were to compete with anyone, we should be with any other person as we are qualified. I do not mean that we need any special treatment; I feel like we need to find a platform that will provide fair competition between other people, maybe that is preferred by the policies. So, I just feel that maybe as much as we have been disadvantaged by policies, maybe there must be provisions that we just know that with regards to these, maybe we are short of having these things."

These tactics highlight the urgent need for commercial

organisations to embrace significant improvements in their policies and analytical frameworks. This would enable hybrid entrepreneurs to fully compete on an even playing field by granting them the ability to exercise their rights and removing the obstacles they encounter.

Inclusive Funding and Mentorship Programs

Thus, hybrid entrepreneurs stress the importance of open funding and more attention to the mentorship programs for such cases. Others feel left out, especially those who were targeting unemployed people, hence a disconnect in services and opportunities. This participant said:

P12: "Grants and funding programs are heavily skewed toward the unemployed, leaving hybrid entrepreneurs unsupported."

Interviews also highlighted difficulties faced by hybrid entrepreneurs in finding workshops and programs that meet their needs, activities that various institutions beyond the state could perform while offering hybrid entrepreneurs accessible and inclusive support.:

P6: "Yeah! This information should be there. These workshops need to be there, and they do not have to be done by the government; they need to be put there by institutions. They should not be exclusive."

Support structures, especially the issue of the mentorship program, were specified as necessary for the hybrid-entrepreneurs, especially given that they needed advice on the efficient balance between the job and business. One participant emphasized:

P12: "Mentorship programs should include hybrid entrepreneurs to help them balance work and business effectively."

As a result, this also calls for a new strategic funding and mentoring foundation announced, to support hybrid entrepreneurs and improve the opportunities they face in both corporate careers and business ventures.

Raising Awareness and Accessibility of Policies

Policy awareness and availability are essential to hybrid entrepreneurs, especially those with inadequate knowledge of available policies. Thus, participants focused on the issues of different marketing communication and advertising aimed at minimising the information gap. One participant pointed out that many people employed in government agencies are not aware of such opportunities:

P4: *"I do not think that they are informed, especially the ones that work for the government. There is a need for marketing or awareness campaigns to make people aware that there are many ways to generate enough income."*

The idea of using social media platforms was proposed as a possible means to reach audiences of more people. Participants suggested that information on policies should be spread on social media by using the various algorithms:

P11: *"This information should be put everywhere... TikTok, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram. Use algorithms to boost such information to people's networks."*

These findings underscore the need for appropriate and efficient preconditioning and postcondition practices to support hybrid entrepreneurs in the context of policy correspondence.

Provision of Skills Development and Training Programs

Education and skills training are necessary commodities for hybrid employees to enable them to cope with challenges that are associated with being both employees and businesspeople. The targeted group supported the necessity of attending short courses and mentorships because these are the useful skills that are not covered in the courses. Indeed, one participant reported their experience:

P6: *"Definitely, short courses and training programs are important. I have done 8 or 9 short courses to equip some of the skills I did not learn. I studied computer science at the University. Some skills I learned through training programs and mentorships from other people."*

Participants also stated that there is a need for universities to take an active part in preparing the hybrid entrepreneurs' business skills even though such courses may not be credited for the qualification. This approach would, on the other hand, equip students with the basic understanding of entrepreneurship. One participant stated the following:

P11: *"The university can help. If you study a certain field of qualification, they can maybe include business short courses for short months, maybe 6, that do not even need to be credited towards your qualification. Just to make them aware that certain jobs are limited. This is to give you the concept of business, how to start your own business, how to run your own business, and things like that. So, the university can do such processes."*

Participants stressed the need to expand knowledge transfer programs targeting hybrid entrepreneurs and other community stakeholders to enable them to make proper decisions regarding handling financial matters and the growth of their enterprises. One participant indicated the following:

P5: *"Hybrid entrepreneurs deserve that; full-time entrepreneurs deserve that; ordinary citizens deserve that kind of knowledge so that they will be able to make proper decisions in terms of how they handle their funds and stuff."*

Conflict of Interest and Workplace Policies

Employers should accept and be open to employing working from home and part-time businesses that do not compete directly with the employees' duties. It was also recommended that this would facilitate the ability of individuals to engage in entrepreneurial activities without fear of losing their jobs. This need was also highlighted by one of the participants, saying that:

P3: *"If a business has no direct conflict with your job, there should be provisions to allow you to continue without fear of losing your job."*

Demanding disclosures about side ventures at work is important, but so is providing all the assistance that hybrid workers require. Working regulations regarding conflicts of interest and sufficient assistance for employees to be successful in their roles as mentors and employees are only a couple of these. One member expressed that by stating:

P8: *"Policies are just a paper with good content written on it because it does give us any business, but all they need is just to declare that we do have business on the side. However, the one thing that one needs to know is that you should understand the conflict of interest; you cannot do business with your employer. However, internal policies from the organization that you are attached to as an employee do not offer us any support, except that we just need to declare. It is through declaration that sometimes you feel like you are trapped in, and maybe they just want to keep tabs on you, but it does not assist you with anything in business; it just disadvantages you as a hybrid entrepreneur."*

These changes are recommendations for raising awareness of workplace policies for hybrid entrepreneurs, who need to be permitted to operate morally and professionally while interacting with or avoiding negative sorts.

Promoting Collaboration Between Government and Private Sector

It is felt that there are insufficient support systems for hybrid entrepreneurship, which raises the importance of collaboration between the government and the private sector. Some of the respondents pointed out that organizations of the private sector may offer support that does not come with governmental programs. This participant stressed the capacity that could come from partnering with the private sector:

P7: *"Partnerships with private sector organizations could fill the gaps where government policies fall short. This will also make it easier to acquire information from resourceful private sectors, especially those owned by youth. I know a company that offers such kind of assistance, including some research."*

Specifically, the private mentorship was said to be most effective in serving hybrid entrepreneurs, as they stressed challenging circumstances and showed even better results than public programs:

P: *"Hybrid entrepreneurs often find better support in private mentorship programs than in public ones."*

The participants also encouraged the integration of partnerships with private organizations, universities, and banks to offer a different

method to support hybrid entrepreneurs and access the necessary tools:

P2: “Ee!... I think collaboration with private sectors like universities, private banks, and others could offer more comprehensive solutions.”

These facts prove that the cooperation between the government and other private firms and organizations must be developed to support hybrid entrepreneurs and help them close the existing gaps, as well as achieve high success rates.

Discussion

The issue of equity in competition for government contracts, as well as the tenders were a common feature in the responses. They underscored that the government needs to introduce policies that encourage businesses with specialisms likely to remain scarce in the future and at the same time, eradicate structural predispositions to subcontracting schemes. Thus, an equitable assessment of the proposed program would provide hybrid entrepreneurs equal opportunities to compete fairly. The above findings support Graafland and Verbruggen's (2022) argument that fair competition promotes the generation of new product varieties and benefits all economic units. Eliminating these biases calls for reforming analytical frameworks of entrepreneurial activity as well as the introduction of pure evaluation criteria, which would enable the representatives of hybrid entrepreneurship to exercise their rights and make their contribution to the economy freely and effectively.

Access to traditional funding streams is a challenge that has been compounded by the exclusion of hybrid entrepreneur programs still today. Society requires more grants and funding programs that are not stigmatised to those who are engaged in paid work. Further, specific mentorship programs designed with hybrid entrepreneurs in mind were deemed critical as they help hybrid entrepreneurs navigate their work and business responsibilities. This brings a positive opinion on the study by Bacq and Alt (2018) whereby they emphasized the aspect of mentorship to enhance the growth of entrepreneurship. This means that institutions should open funding opportunities and set up mentorship programs that will provide additional support services and bring both ends of the hybrid scale together.

Ignorance of these policies and programs by these hybrid entrepreneurs was another phenomenon that came out of the study. Participants recommended that message dissemination should be done through TikTok, improving the use of WhatsApp, and by using algorithms such as hashtags, which will post messages on Instagram to larger audiences. According to Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2015), access to information plays an important intermediary role in supporting these businesses. Targeted campaigns and outreach programs that raise awareness can keep hybrid entrepreneurs adequately informed, increasing the effectiveness of policies as a result.

There is a need to train hybrid entrepreneurs to meet the unique difficulties of juggling employment and entrepreneurship. This formed a major opinion where participants proposed short courses, mentorship, and skills transfer programs. Universities were named as institutions which can introduce basic business courses into their programs and among non-credit ones to contribute to combined business ventures. This view corresponds with the views of Galvao, Marques, and Ferreira (2020) who have the strong belief that

education and skills growth are central to sustainable ventures. Helping to increase the accessibility of training programs can help to enable hybrid entrepreneurs to make better choices and improve the functioning of their enterprises.

Specifically, participants stressed the importance of having policies for hybrid entrepreneurship without exclusion from work obligations. Viable solutions were to permit subordinate stakeholders, such as employees, to engage in other income generating activities that are independent of a corporation but relevant to it, while providing structural measures to guarantee compliance with ethical norms. According to Noll (2021), there is some equity in overregulation, and the level of freedom that proper entrepreneurship deserves. Adjusting the labour related public policies regarding hybrid entrepreneurship can offer better opportunities to support flexible working communities and thus make them more efficient and entrepreneurial.

Interactions between the public and private sectors were noted to be important in closing the remaining gaps in support for hybrid entrepreneurs. Respondents stated that private tutor services and cooperation with universities and banks offer better solutions than an open call. Elnadi and Gheith (2021) explain the importance of collaborative ecosystems in the development of entrepreneurship. Hybrid entrepreneurs can combine government resources and talents from the private sector to improve their competitiveness.

Conclusion

The most recommended strategies to ensure the effectiveness of public policies include fostering fair competition and reducing bias, ensuring inclusive funding and mentorship programs, raising awareness and accessibility of policies, providing skills development and training programs, limiting conflict of interest and workplace policies, and promoting collaboration between government and private sector.

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